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Global Value Chains in Time of Sanctions

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Abstract

In recent years, there has been a proliferation of economic sanctions imposed by the United States, the main proponent of such sanctions. Several authors have questioned their effectiveness, as targeted countries may try to evade or circumvent them. Economic sanctions have complex effects, particularly on the global value chain (GVC), which reflects the interdependence of economies. Participation in global value chains can create loopholes that allow sanctioned countries to mitigate their impact. This may be even more the case if sanctions are laxly applied. On the other hand, sanctions may permanently lock countries into low-value-added activities. This study examines the complex effects of US economic sanctions on the participation of targeted countries in global value chains. Using a panel of 102 developing countries from 1990 to 2018 and applying the entropy balancing method, it finds that US economic sanctions reduce participation in global value chains by 1.06 percentage points relative to non-targeted countries. Results show that trade and financial sanctions hinder global value chain participation, with a sanctioned country losing almost 5 years of progress in the GVC. The effects are more pronounced for highly trade-dependent and resource-rich economies, while countries with strong financial systems are more resilient. This impact is supported by an alternative method involving the use of an instrumental variable estimator. Relying on other alternative econometric methods does not change the main results. Lower foreign direct investment (FDI), reduced innovation capacity, exclusion from international financial networks and increased macroeconomic uncertainty, as measured by inflation and real effective exchange rate volatility, are the main drivers of the impact of economic sanctions on participation in global value chains.

Keywords: Economic Sanctions • Global Value Chains • Entropy Balancing • Developing countries

JEL Codes: F51 • F60 • C21 • O10

“US sanctions are particularly harmful because of their extraterritorial application, the global importance of the US economy, the dominance of the Dollar as a global currency, and because unilateral sanctions require less political consensus than sanctions by the United Nations and can therefore cause collateral damage with less political resistance.” — Gutmann et al. (2023).

1 Introduction

Over the past decades, international sanctions have become an increasingly common tool of statecraft used by countries to exert political pressure on target nations (Morgan et al., 2023) and encourage them to change their behaviour. They are designed to respond to alleged violations of international law, human rights abuses or non-compliance with international standards. Their main objectives are to deter actions deemed unacceptable, to punish the states responsible and to encourage a return to compliance with international obligations (Hatipoglu et al., 2023). Recent examples of economic sanctions include the measures imposed by the United States (US) and the European Union (EU) on Russia following its annexation of Crimea in 2014 and Ukraine’s invasion in 2022, as well as the trade sanctions exchanged between the US and China during their trade tensions from 2018 to 2020. Moreover, as geopolitical tensions have escalated, the number of active sanctions reached an all-time high in 2022, with over 400 sanctions in effect—the most extensive total recorded since 1950 (Syropoulos et al., 2024). These sanctions, designed to compel changes in the target country’s policies, are often seen as a less aggressive alternative to military intervention, aiming to inflict economic harm without resorting to violence (Cortright and Lopez, 2000; Hufbauer et al., 2009).

As the use of economic sanctions has surged globally, the literature on the subject has evolved both theoretically and empirically. On the theoretical side, researchers rely heavily on negotiation and game-theoretic models to provide insights into the conditions for sanctions’ success, their occurrence, and their effects on both the sanctioned and sanctioning countries.¹ More recently, Janeba (2024) suggests that economic sanctions can be the result of the presence of harmful activities such as nuclear weapons development or international terrorism sponsorship. Joshi et al. (2024) explore these dynamics in this field, emphasize the harmful effects of sanctions and suggest that sanctions are more effective when they target imports. On the empirical side, scholars have focused on the economic, social, and institutional effects of economic sanctions on target states. For example, Neuenkirch and Neumeier (2015) show that the UN and US sanctions decrease the real GDP per capita growth of the target state by an average of 2.3-3.5 and 0.5-0.9 percentage points, respectively. Similarly, Hufbauer et al. (2009) find that sanctioned economies experienced an average 3% decline in gross national output and a 37% inflation rate. Gutmann et al. (2023) show that sanctions reduce economic growth, trade and foreign direct investment (FDI), while Laudati and Pesaran (2023) estimate that sanctions could account for up to 60% of output growth forecast error variance of Iran. Scholars also show sanctions’ negative impacts on international trade, exchange rate volatility (Haidar, 2017; Afe-

¹see, e.g., Kaempfer and Lowenberg, 1988; Eaton and Engers, 1999; Tsebelis, 1990; Lacy and Niou, 2004; Ye and Zhang, 2024, among others.

sorgbor, 2019), foreign direct investment (Mirkina, 2018), and firm performance (Ahn and Ludema, 2020; Crozet et al., 2021). Social effects include reduced life expectancy (Gutmann et al., 2021), worsen human rights (Peksen, 2009), heightened poverty and income inequality (Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016; Afesorgbor and Mahadevan, 2016; Moteng et al., 2023) and consolidated authoritarian rule (Peksen and Drury, 2010; Oechslin, 2014). While the literature highlights the adverse effects of sanctions on target countries, research also reveals their counterproductive impacts on sanctioning countries through two main mechanisms: counter-sanctions and trade diversion. Sanctioned countries often respond by imposing counter-sanctions and restricting trade with sanctioning nations.² Additionally, sanctions can divert bilateral trade between sanctioning and sanctioned countries to third parties. For instance, restrictions on targeted goods raise prices, encouraging third countries to fill the supply gap, while import sanctions push target countries to seek alternative export markets, reshaping global trade flows (Hufbauer et al., 2009; Shingal, 2024).

A growing body of literature—which mainly focuses on particular countries or regions—has examined the effects of sanctions, particularly trade sanctions, on global value chains (GVCs). For instance, Bellora and Fontagné (2020) and Yang (2023) show that trade sanctions from the US-China trade war have negatively affected both parties, both in terms of welfare and GVC participation (i.e., through limited access to inputs and markets). Crozet et al. (2021) analyze monthly data from French exporting firms and show that new sanctions reduce the likelihood of firms exporting to targeted markets, while simultaneously prompting them to redirect exports to neighboring countries (i.e., nearshoring or friend-shoring). Similarly, Bruno et al. (2024) find that the effects of China's trade sanctions on GVCs in South Africa vary depending on the perspective—whether from the buyer's (backward) or seller's (forward) side—highlighting the key role of comparative advantages in shaping the sanctions' effects.

While these studies contribute to understanding the effects of trade sanctions at the firm level or in particular countries or regions, our study extends the literature by comprehensively analyzing the effects of economic - trade and financial - sanctions on developing countries' participation in global value chains. GVCs—characterized by the fragmentation of production processes across multiple countries—have become a cornerstone of global trade, offering significant opportunities for economic growth and development. On the one hand, economic sanctions can disrupt a target country's ability to participate in global value chains while enhancing macroeconomic instability, reducing foreign direct investment, disrupting the domestic financial system or staining political relations. On the other hand, several authors question the effectiveness of economic sanctions since target countries can try to evade and circumvent economic sanctions. Our study provides a comprehensive analysis of how US economic sanctions affect the participation of target countries in GVCs, using the broadest country coverage dataset on GVC that is particularly suitable when studying for developing countries (Mancini et al., 2024). Building on the existing literature, we shift our focus to US sanctions for several reasons. First, the United States has historically been the world's most frequent user of international sanctions, responsible for nearly one-third of all sanctions imposed (Felbermayr et al., 2022; Morgan et al., 2023). Second, following the Cold War, the United States emerged as the predominant global

²See Russia's example from Korhonen (2019) and Nguyen and Do (2021).

hegemonic power (Adam and Tsarsitalidou, 2019). Additionally, the United States not only leads in imposing sanctions unilaterally but also substantially influences sanction initiatives by entities like the United Nations and various coalitions (Morgan et al., 2023). Finally, in recent sanctions against Russia, the United States has taken a leadership role, effectively “showing the way” for its allies. Even if focusing on US sanctions relies on the existing literature, it may overlook the wide range of sanctions imposed by other nations and international organizations. To address this, we conduct a robustness test by accounting for sanctions from the European Union (EU) and the United Nations (UN) and a comprehensive measure that captures all sanctions globally.

Our paper offers a comprehensive approach, i.e., a cross-country analysis, to examine the effect of US sanctions on GVCs’ participation in countries exposed to US sanctions (i.e., the treatment group) compared to non-sanctioned countries (i.e., the control group). To deal with the selection bias as sanctions are not imposed randomly, we rely on an impact evaluation method, namely the entropy balancing method—a matching approach developed by Hainmueller (2012) that allows to create reliable counterfactuals comprised of countries not exposed to sanctions that are similar to the treatment group with regard to macro- as well as socioeconomic characteristics that potentially correlate with the imposition of US sanctions and the GVCs’ participation. Using a sample of 102 countries from 1990 to 2018, our results reveal that US sanctions hamper GVCs participation in sanctioned countries compared to non-sanctioned countries. These results remain robust to various tests, including alternative samples, alternative specifications, placebo tests, and alternative methods. Moreover, our paper examines several sources of heterogeneity, focusing on the nature of sanctions (e.g., trade vs. financial) and key macroeconomic conditions. Specifically, our findings indicate that (i) trade sanctions have a slightly greater effect than financial sanctions, and (ii) the effects of US sanctions are more severe in countries with high trade openness and abundant natural resources, whereas they are less pronounced in economies with a well-developed financial system. Finally, our empirical analysis reveals that the adverse effects of US sanctions on GVC participation operate through channels such as reduction of FDI inflows and innovation capacity alongside rising inflation and exchange rate volatility.

This paper contributes to two main strands of literature. First, our work is closely related to the empirical literature on the adverse effects of economic sanctions. As mentioned earlier, the literature on economic sanctions has predominantly focused on economic, social, and institutional outcomes, and only a few scholars have examined their effects on international trade (Afesorgbor, 2019; Gutmann et al., 2023). Recent papers have attempted to go beyond international trade by studying the effects of sanctions on the global value chain. However, none of these papers have examined this relationship directly and at a global level since they are limited to one type of economic sanction, i.e., trade sanctions (Nosratabadi, 2023), or focusing on specific cases of countries facing sanctions effects (Mamonov and Pestova, 2022; Crozet et al., 2021). By identifying key mechanisms—such as the reduction of FDI entry, the decline in innovation capacity, and macroeconomic instability—our paper is a first step toward a better understanding of how US sanctions shape GVCs’ participation, going beyond Le et al. (2022). While Le et al. (2022) applies a gravity model to analyze the relationship between sanctions and GVCs using a bilateral trade-based measure of participation, this approach

remains limited in capturing the true nature of GVC integration. GVC participation is not merely an extension of bilateral trade but a complex network of production fragmentation across multiple countries, where intermediate goods cross several borders before reaching their final destination. By focusing on bilateral trade relationships, [Le et al. \(2022\)](#) does not fully account for the interdependencies shaping global production networks. In contrast, using the UNCTAD-EORA Global Supply Chain dataset that makes it possible to track the evolution of countries' integration into GVCs by country, our study adopts a systemic approach that evaluates the response of participation of countries in GVCs to economic sanctions beyond pairwise trade flows. In doing so, this paper bridges the gap between sanction studies and the evolving literature on GVCs, offering a novel contribution to understanding how economic sanctions reshape today's modern economies. Second, our paper also contributes to the literature analyzing the determinants of GVCs' participation. Several works have shed light on the determinants of GVCs' participation, highlighting factors such as factor endowments, geography, political stability, liberal trade policies, foreign direct investment, and domestic industrial capacity (see, for example, [Anràs \(2020\)](#); [Anràs and De Gortari \(2020\)](#); [Anràs and Chor \(2022\)](#); [Fernandes et al. \(2022\)](#), among others). Our paper complements existing research by carefully focusing on the role of foreign policy instruments, such as economic sanctions, and provides evidence that these can exert important adverse effects on the dynamic of GVCs' participation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides theoretical arguments for why sanctions may affect GVCs' participation in target countries. Section 3 reports some stylized facts. Section 4 describes the identification strategy and data. Section 5 discusses our main findings, while section 6 performs some sensitivity checks. Sections 7 and 8 deal with heterogeneity analysis and the validity of transmission channels. Section 9 concludes and provides some policy implications.

2 Theoretical discussions

Economic sanctions may affect GVCs through four relevant channels, namely, the reduction of FDI entry, the exclusion from international financial networks, the decline in innovation capacity, and macroeconomic instability.

A well-functioning global value chain relies to some extent on the seamless flow of foreign direct investment (FDI), a critical driver of GVCs' participation. The literature highlights the positive role of FDI in GVCs' participation, as it provides local firms with access to technology, managerial expertise, and financing, thereby enhancing their competitiveness ([Martínez-Galán and Fontoura, 2019](#); [Adarov and Stehrer, 2021](#); [Fernandes et al., 2022](#)). Moreover, by easing financial constraints and fostering innovation, FDI strengthens a country's ability to meet global production standards ([Chen et al., 2015](#); [Kee, 2015](#); [Kowalski, 2015](#); [Kee and Tang, 2016](#)). However, economic sanctions disrupt this dynamic by increasing foreign investors' risk aversion, generating economic and political uncertainty, and prompting capital withdrawal ([McLean and Whang, 2010](#); [Lektzian and Biglaiser, 2013](#); [Barry and Kleinberg, 2015](#); [Shin et al., 2016](#)). For instance, [Mirкина \(2018\)](#) finds that economic sanctions led to an average decline in FDI by 15.8% in the short run and 11.1% in the long run across 184 countries from 1970 to 2010. The fall in FDI will in turn have an impact on domestic firms. As a result, sanc-

tions deprive local firms of the external resources necessary for upgrading production processes and meeting international standards, thereby limiting their participation in competitive GVC segments. Moreover, the loss of foreign partnerships restricts access to trade networks, further isolating target countries from global markets.

Beyond access to capital, economic sanctions can severely disrupt global value chain participation by excluding target countries from international financial networks. Sanction-related measures such as asset freezes, restrictions on currency use in international markets, and exclusion from international payment systems (e.g., SWIFT) impose significant barriers to trade and investment. For instance, [Afesorgbor \(2019\)](#) suggests that these financial restrictions can substantially hinder international trade by cutting off local firms from essential liquidity sources. Freezing assets deprives local firms of critical capital needed to fund their operations, investments, and global trade, thus hindering their competitiveness and limiting their ability to sustain commercial relationships. Likewise, restrictions on currency use in international markets complicate foreign exchange transactions and increase the cost of importing raw materials or intermediate goods necessary for production. Moreover, exclusion from global payment networks financially isolates sanctioned countries, creating inefficiencies in financial flows, increasing transaction costs, and delaying supply chain operations. As a result, these financial disruptions further constrain the ability of local firms to integrate into the highly fragmented and interconnected value chains.

Innovation is another channel through which economic sanctions might shape participation in GVCs. Indeed, innovation plays a central role in shaping a country's integration into global value chains. By enhancing competitiveness and ensuring compliance with international quality and efficiency standards, innovation allows firms to move into higher-value segments of GVCs ([Morrison et al., 2008](#); [Montalbano et al., 2018](#)). In particular, firms that invest in technological, organizational, or production innovations are better positioned to access new markets and establish stronger linkages within global networks. Going one step further, innovation facilitates knowledge transfer and technological upgrading, especially for developing countries that rely on imported inputs from advanced economies ([Tajoli and Felice, 2018](#)). However, economic sanctions may pose significant barriers to this process. In fact, some scholars show that economic sanctions decrease the innovation capacity of target countries by reducing trade and capital flows ([Wen et al., 2024](#)). On the one hand, the decline in trade flows due to sanctions reduces FDI inflows, exposing domestic firms to financial constraints that hinder their innovation capacity ([Khachoo and Sharma, 2016](#); [Golikova and Kuznetsov, 2017](#)). On the other hand, trade restrictions resulting from sanctions prevent local firms from accessing cutting-edge technologies through knowledge spillovers and learning effects, ultimately increasing R&D costs, weakening competitiveness, and stifling innovation ([Damijan and Kostevc, 2015](#)). Consequently, these adverse effects of economic sanctions on a country's ability to innovate could, in turn, negatively impact its integration into global value chains.

Out of these previous channels, the macroeconomic instability induced by economic sanctions might pose another significant threat to GVCs' participation. Sanctions often trigger economic shocks in target countries by fueling inflation and exchange rate volatility ([Heine-Ellison, 2001](#); [Hufbauer et al., 2009](#); [Fadaee and Derakhshan, 2015](#); [Ghorbani Dastgerdi et al., 2018](#); [Wang et al., 2019](#); [Itskhoki](#)

and Mukhin, 2022). This instability may manifest in rising production costs (Kandilov and Leblebicioğlu, 2011), declining export competitiveness (Demir, 2013; Rashid and Waqar, 2017), and inefficiencies within key production segments. Moreover, increased transaction costs and supply chain delays—particularly in industries that rely on global inputs—further weaken firms’ ability to compete internationally (Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016). In extreme cases, local firms may be forced to exit GVCs entirely, unable to meet the stringent cost and quality requirements set by international partners. Furthermore, the economic uncertainty generated by sanctions erodes trust between international trade partners, fragmenting the effective functioning of GVCs. As sanctions extend their reach across interconnected economies, they disrupt both backward and forward linkages, negatively impacting GVCs’ involvement. More specifically, exchange rate volatility increases the risks associated with export contracts, forcing firms to adopt costly hedging strategies or withdraw from volatile markets (temporarily or definitely), which may ultimately limit their growth potential within GVCs.

Considering these factors—the reduction in FDI inflows, the exclusion from international financial networks, the decline in innovation capacity, and macroeconomic instability (through rising inflation and exchange rate volatility)—we can believe that economic sanctions may negatively affect countries’ participation in GVCs. However, although all these arguments point to a negative effect of sanctions, two others may imply the opposite (Bruno et al., 2024). First, sanctions can disrupt value chains in ways that incentivize diversification (e.g., through near-shoring or friend-shoring). When a country is cut off from a key supplier due to sanctions, it may seek alternative sources for inputs and new markets, ultimately fostering greater participation in global value chains (GVCs) (Mityakov et al., 2013; Raymond et al., 2022). Second, the so-called “third-party nation channel” operates through both “general equilibrium effects” and “extra-territorial” sanctions. General equilibrium effects arise when economic disruptions caused by sanctions strengthen trade relationships with third countries, effectively rerouting trade flows. Meanwhile, extra-territorial sanctions impose penalties on non-sanctioned countries that engage in economic activities with the sanctioned state, further reshaping global trade dynamics (Morgan et al., 2023). These two mechanisms are closely intertwined, as diversification efforts often interact with third-party nation effects, ultimately influencing the broader structure of GVC participation. All that said, the effects of sanctions on GVCs’ participation remain unclear.

3 Stylized facts

Figure 1 shows the trend of US economic sanctions (trade or financial) over the study period (1990-2018). For each year during this period, we both identify the total number of US sanctions and the number of countries under US sanctions. Several distinct time spans with shifting trends can be identified. In the early 1990s (1990-1993), as the United States increasingly relied on sanctions as a key foreign policy tool to coerce foreign governments, the number of US sanctions began rising continuously. For example, in 1990, US sanctions were imposed on countries like Iraq following its invasion of Kuwait, marking the start of over a decade of economic restrictions led by the US. Other examples include US sanctions imposed on (i) Haiti due to the military coup that overthrew Pres-

ident Jean-Bertrand Aristide at the end of 1991 and (ii) Yugoslavia in response to the Yugoslav Wars and widespread human rights violations in 1992. After peaking in the mid-1990s, the trend shifted notably, with the number of sanctioned countries steadily declining until 2005. This decline coincided with growing humanitarian concerns, particularly in response to the widespread harm sanctions inflicted on innocent civilians. This led to a decrease in the use of such sanctions and a reassessment of their effectiveness as a tool of foreign policy. However, the imposition of US sanctions surged again, continuing until the middle of President Obama's second term. Following this peak, sanctions declined through 2016. Yet from 2017 onward, the number of active sanctions rose sharply once more, continuing through the end of the sample period. This resurgence aligns with President Trump's tenure, during which his administration aggressively expanded unilateral sanctions against multiple countries, including Venezuela, Iran, North Korea, and Russia, among others. Overall, the number of countries under US sanctions has exhibited a fluctuating yet increasing trend since 1990. Likewise, in figure 2, we observe that the number of sanctions has followed the same trend over the study period. However, the number of sanctions has increased more rapidly than the number of sanctioned countries over the period, likely due to a "diversification" of sanctioning tools. In other words, the US administration has imposed multiple types of sanctions on the same target countries. In our analysis, we focus specifically on trade and financial sanctions because we consider that they are the most likely to affect trade flows. Overall, we interpret these trends as a clear indication of the growing use of US sanctions as a tool of coercive diplomacy. Consequently, one might expect the economic impact of these sanctions to rise as well, affecting factors that shape today's modern economy, i.e., global value chains.

Figure 1: Evolution of the number of countries with US sanctions (1990-2018).

Source: Authors, from GSDB Dataset.

Figure 2: Evolution of the number of US sanctions (1990-2018).

Source: Authors, from GSDB Dataset.

Figure 3 shows the difference in GVCs' participation for treated units (countries under the US sanctions) and untreated units. Participation in GVCs is measured by an index ranging from 0 to 100, where lower values indicate low participation and higher values indicate high participation. This figure reveals that, on average, participation in GVCs is lower for treated units than untreated units

(43.25. vs. 45.41, respectively). This 2.16-point difference may seem small, but it represents 4.75% of the untreated units' average GVCs participation, which is not negligible. Moreover, the difference in GVCs' participation between the two groups is statistically significant at the usual thresholds (t-test= 4.23; p-value = 0.00). Although significant, this correlation does not provide a causal relationship between US sanctions and GVCs participation for our sample countries.

Figure 3: Average index of GVCs' participation with and without sanctions (1990-2018).

Source : Authors, from UNCTAD Dataset.

4 Identification strategy

4.1 Data

To examine the effect of US economic sanctions on Global Value Chains (GVCs) participation in developing countries, we compile annual panel data of 102 developing countries from 1990 to 2018. Two factors have conditioned the time horizon: (i) the intensification of the use of US economic sanctions as a foreign policy tool in the early 1990s, alongside the growing interest in GVCs among economists and policymakers, and (ii) data ending in 2018 for our outcome variable (GVCs' participation).³ We focus on developing countries because GVC integration has fundamentally reshaped their production structures and labor markets, offering a unique opportunity for economic transformation. Unlike in the past, when countries needed to develop entire industries to participate in global trade, GVCs allowed developing economies to integrate by specializing in specific tasks while leaving more complex stages of production to other countries. This specialization has pushed their firms to become more productive and expand, boosting overall productivity while also improving access to high-quality and cost-effective inputs. Moreover, linkages with foreign firms facilitate the transfer of managerial and technological best practices, further enhancing competitiveness. However, while GVC participation is well-known to accelerate income growth and contribute to poverty reduction in the developing world, it also presents structural challenges. These include a bias towards skilled labor and increased vulnerability to external shocks—factors that can exacerbate inequality and affect overall development outcomes. Given that economic sanctions can act as a major shock to trade and investment flows,

³Even though the Global Sanctions Database (GSDB) provides data on sanctions from 1990 to 2023, we are unable to use the full-time coverage because data on GVC participation is only available from 1990 to 2018.

studying their impact within this context may provide some policy implications on how geopolitically induced disruptions in GVCs' participation can have far-reaching consequences for economic development in developing countries. Moreover, sanctions could be one of the factors slowing down the integration of these countries into global value chains, even as their integration has continued for the past two decades. The definition of developing countries follows the IMF's classification.

Our outcome variable is a country's participation in global value chains (GVCs' participation), measured as an index of participation. This participation index combines Backward and Forward linkages, capturing distinct aspects of a country's role in global production networks (Doamba, 2025). We rely on the UNCTAD-EORA Global Supply Chain database (Casella et al., 2019),⁴ which provides key indicators, specifically foreign value added (FVA) embedded in a country's exports (backward participation) and domestic value added (DVX) embedded in foreign countries' exports (forward linkages), that allow us to compute the index. Backward and Forward participation are constructed as follows:

$$Backward_{it} = \frac{FVA_{it}}{Gross\ Export_{it}} \quad (1)$$

$$Forward_{it} = \frac{DVX_{it}}{Gross\ Export_{it}} \quad (2)$$

Following, e.g., Tajoli and Felice, 2018; Tian et al., 2022, among others, these two components are combined to define GVC Index:

$$GVC = Backward + Forward \quad (3)$$

This aggregated index thus provides a comprehensive measure of a country's participation in global value chains, capturing its integration and positioning across different stages of the production process, from initial input supplier (upstream) to final product assembler (downstream). The index ranges from 0 to 100, where lower values indicate low participation and higher values indicate high participation.

The data on international sanctions are sourced from the Global Sanctions Database (GSDB) (Kirikakha et al., 2021; Syropoulos et al., 2024), a well-known dataset widely used in the literature (see, e.g., Wang et al., 2019; Felbermayr et al., 2020; Arslanalp et al., 2023; Morgan et al., 2023)). The GSDB documents each sanction case for every year in which active sanctions are imposed by individual countries, groups of countries, or international organizations, such as the European Union (EU) or the United Nations (UN). This comprehensive dataset provides critical insights into the dynamics of international relations and the effectiveness of sanctions as a policy tool. It encompasses all bilateral, multilateral, and plurilateral sanctions globally, featuring 1,325 sanction cases from 1950 to 2022. It concentrates on three primary dimensions: the type of sanction, the sender, and the objec-

⁴The UNCTAD-EORA Database includes data on the inputs and outputs of different industries at global level, making it possible to trace value-added flows between countries.

tive of the sanction. Sanction cases are classified into six distinct types, including trade sanctions, financial sanctions, travel restrictions, arms sanctions, military assistance sanctions, and other forms of sanctions. For each case, the database outlines nine potential policy objectives: inducing policy change, destabilizing a regime, resolving territorial disputes, preventing wars, ending ongoing conflicts, combating terrorism, addressing human rights abuses, restoring democracy, and other related aims. However, only trade and financial sanctions are relevant to our study because they directly affect global value chains (GVCs) by disrupting trade flows and financial transactions. Trade sanctions typically impose restrictions on imports, exports, or both, aiming to exert economic pressure on a target country to influence its behavior. In contrast, financial sanctions target financial transactions, assets, or access to international banking systems, seeking to constrain a target country’s ability to fund its activities or transfer money across borders. As a result, these types of sanctions can be harmful to GVCs’ participation in target countries. Then, using the GSDB dataset, we construct our treatment variable—US economic sanctions (trade or financial sanctions)—which takes a value of 1 if country i is subject to US trade sanctions or US financial sanctions in a given year t , and zero otherwise. 60 countries and a total of 476 country-years observations in our dataset were subject to US economic sanctions. Table A7 in the Appendix provides a complete list of countries while table A8 offers detailed information on the specific types of sanctions imposed on these countries.

Our choice of control variables broadly follows [Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016](#); [Gutmann et al., 2021](#); [Apeti and Edoh, 2024](#) among others, that have also employed entropy balancing to assess the impact of US economic sanctions on different outcomes. As mentioned earlier, we select a control group of untreated units that closely matches the treatment group on relevant pretreatment characteristics, ensuring comparability on average. The first group of variables relates to factors that capture the economic environment, including economic growth, inflation, and trade openness. The second group of variables controls for factors related to economic development, such as human capital and population size. The last group of variables controls for political factors, such as the degree of democracy, the number of coups d’état, and armed conflict. All these covariates are lagged by one year to overcome reverse causality issues. Table A9 reports their descriptive statistics, while Table A10 provides a complete description and source of these variables and their source.

4.2 Identification strategy

This study aims at establishing a causal effect of economic sanctions on participation in GVCs. The econometric literature mostly relies on bilateral data estimated using a gravity model. Such an approach is less relevant to our study, which focuses on GVCs’ participation. Our measure of GVC participation, derived from the UNCTAD-EORA Global Supply Chain database, is not structured as bilateral data, necessitating a different identification approach. Consequently, we follow the strand of the literature that assesses the effect of sanctions through a treatment-effect approach, considering US economic sanctions as a treatment and country-year observations as units of analysis. We exploit variations in the timing of US economic sanctions across countries, as captured by the following equation:

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 US\ sanctions_{i,t} + \beta_2 X_{i,t} + \mu_i + \phi_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

$Y_{i,t}$ is the outcome variable and denotes GVCs' participation in country i at time t . $US\ sanctions_{i,t}$ is a dummy variable capturing our treatment variable. It takes the value of one when a country i is subjected to US economic sanctions (trade or financial) at period t , and zero otherwise. $X_{i,t}$ is a set of pretreatment covariates (described earlier in subsection 4.1); μ_i captures country-specific effects; ϕ_t captures time-fixed effects. Finally, $\epsilon_{i,t}$ represents the idiosyncratic error term.

Eq.4 represents an ordinary difference-in-differences (DID) specification with a set of covariates and fixed effects. Since the imposition of US sanctions depends on many factors—some associated with the US administration but others associated with country-specific characteristics (e.g., institutional framework)—this decision is not exogenous. For instance, the US administration might believe that imposing sanctions may foster democratic change in a country, protect democracy, or destabilize an autocratic regime, allowing them to trigger changes in target countries. If the choice to impose US economic sanctions were determined only by observable factors, then the covariates specified in Eq.4 would be enough to identify the effect of US economic sanctions on GVCs' participation. Because some of these relevant factors are unobservable, we cannot account for them. As a result, our analysis may be subject to a self-selection problem, raising potential endogeneity concerns in our baseline specification. Consequently, it would be misleading to estimate the effect of US economic sanctions on GVCs' participation by simply comparing the participation of GVCs before and after the adoption of the imposition of US economic sanctions. Therefore, using traditional econometric techniques to estimate the impact of such policies could, therefore, lead to biased estimates. Also, the panel structure of our data makes it wise to account for country-specific and time-specific unobservable factors that can jointly determine US economic sanctions and GVCs' participation.

Because the choice of the US administration to impose an economic sanction can be correlated with a set of observable variables that also affect the outcome variable (GVCs' participation), it is necessary to carefully construct a control group. To address selection bias, we can use a set of observable variables to identify non-sanctioned countries that closely match sanctioned ones within the sample rather than treating all non-sanctioned countries equally. Against this background, our identification strategy follows a more innovative impact evaluation approach, namely entropy balancing developed by [Hainmueller \(2012\)](#), which combines matching with difference-in-difference in a two-step estimation procedure. This method is widely used in the economic literature on sanctions, including [Neuenkirch and Neumeier \(2016\)](#) to assess the effect of US sanctions on poverty, [Gutmann et al. \(2021\)](#) to evaluate the effect of economic sanctions on life expectancy, [Gutmann et al. \(2023\)](#) to analyze the effect of sanctions on economic growth and its components, [Wen et al. \(2024\)](#) and [Apeti and Edoh \(2024\)](#) to investigate, respectively, the impact of sanctions on innovation and sovereign debt default. Moreover, a non-exhaustive list of macroeconomic literature also employs entropy balancing.⁵

⁵See, for example, [Huang and Yeh, 2014](#); [Ogrokhina and Rodriguez, 2019](#); [Balima, 2020](#); [Balima and Sy, 2021](#); [Caselli and Wingender, 2021](#); [Combes et al., 2024a](#); [Kinda and Mien, 2024](#); [Ogrokhina and Rodriguez, 2024](#); [Sawadogo, 2024](#), among others.

The entropy balancing method is implemented in two main stages. The first step involves computing and assigning annual weights to the untreated units based on the observable characteristics (covariates). Notice that weights for treated units are 1, while observations for untreated units have a positive weight obtained from the first step of the matching approach. These weights must satisfy defined balance constraints imposed on the covariates, implying that the re-weighted control group's sample moments correspond exactly to the treatment group's corresponding moments. Consequently, this first step of entropy balancing creates a counterfactual group whose difference from the treatment group will be the imposition of sanctions, conditional on the defined covariates in Eq.4. In our analysis, balance constraints require equal covariate means between the treatment and control groups, ensuring that we pair non-sanctioned countries with sanctioning countries that are as similar as possible in terms of covariates (observable characteristics). The second step uses the weights computed from the first step in our ordinary DID regression (Eq.4), implying in that way that treated and matched control groups are incorporated into a fixed-effects specification to account for both observable and unobservable characteristics. Since entropy balancing computes annual weights, it effectively handles the panel structure of the data. Then, we are able to include country and time-fixed effects in our Eq.4. [Smith and Todd \(2005\)](#) argue that this approach of combining matching with difference-in-difference (fixed effects) has the advantage of gauging unobserved time-invariant differences in the outcome variable between sanctioned and non-sanctioned countries, which standard matching estimators fail to do. As noticed by [Heckman et al. \(1998\)](#), failure to account for these differences can produce biased estimates of the ATT. All that said, entropy balancing allows us to identify the effect of US sanctions on GVCs' participation by comparing sanctioned countries and non-sanctioned countries that are similar on observable variables while controlling for country and year-fixed effects.

By combining both matching and regression approaches, entropy balancing offers several advantages over existing methods ([Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016](#)). One key advantage over "simple" regression-based approaches and propensity score matching methods is that entropy balancing is non-parametric. This means there is no need to specify an econometric model for the outcome variable or selection into treatment. As a result, potential misspecifications, such as those related to the functional form of the econometric model, are discarded, reducing the likelihood of biased estimates. Moreover, unlike regression-based analyses, treatment effects estimates based on entropy balancing are not affected by multicollinearity, as the reweighting scheme orthogonalizes the covariates with respect to the treatment indicator. Furthermore, unlike other matching methods, entropy balancing ensures a high balance between the treatment and control groups, even when dealing with small samples. This refined approach creates a synthetic control group that closely mirrors the treatment group, enhancing estimation accuracy in the second step ([Hainmueller, 2012](#)).⁶ Despite the advantages of entropy balancing over more traditional approaches, it is essential to note that it may have some limits. Even if Eq.4 requires controlling for factors affecting the imposition of US sanctions and GVCs, entropy balancing may, in practice, fail to control potential endogeneity biases resulting from

⁶For further details on advantages of entropy balancing, see, for example, [Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016](#); [Apeti, 2023](#); [Ogrokhina and Rodriguez, 2024](#), among others.

unobserved time-varying factors that may affect both US sanctions and GVCs, as well as the reverse causality problem that may exist between the treatment variable and the outcome variable (Apeti, 2023; Sawadogo, 2024). To test the sensitivity of our conclusions, we complement the entropy balancing approach with alternative estimation methods including an instrumental variable estimator.

5 Results

In this section, we present the descriptive statistics for the covariates of our baseline specification and discuss our benchmark results.

5.1 Covariates Balance

Prior to any formal econometric analyses, let us focus on some descriptive statistics, presented in Table 1, related to the first step of entropy balancing. Panel A displays a simple comparison of sample means, before weighting for all matching covariates, between treated units (column [1]) and untreated units (column [2]). Column [3] reports the difference in means between these two groups. The figures reveal notable differences in nearly all relevant pretreatment characteristics between periods with active sanctions and those without. Indeed, sanctioned countries are characterized by (i) a low degree of openness, (ii) a larger population, and (iii) tend to have poorer institutional quality, evidenced by lower democracy levels and a higher frequency of coups d'état and conflicts. These differences across sanctioned and non-sanctioned countries highlight the importance of selecting an appropriate control group via a matching approach. Panel B shows in columns [1] and [2] the sample mean obtained by entropy balancing after weighting between the treatment and the synthetic groups, and column [3] reports the difference between the two. The analysis reveals the effectiveness of entropy balancing as the difference shown in Panel A disappears. As a result, entropy balancing allows us to build an ideal control group closely similar to sanctioned countries regarding the mean values of the pretreatment covariates.

Table 1: Covariates Balancing

	[1]	[2]	[3] = [2] - [1]	[4]	[5]
Panel A : Before Weighting	Under US Sanctions	Without US Sanctions	Difference	t-Test	p-Value
Lag. GDP per Capita Growth	3.92	4.22	0.30	0.68	0.49
Lag. Inflation	19.4	22.6	3.20	0.48	0.62
Lag. Trade Openness	55.98	71.5	15.52	8.05	0.00
Lag. Democracy	3.50	3.68	0.18	1.88	0.06
Lag. Human Capital	2.16	2.20	0.04	1.31	0.19
Lag. Population (Log)	17.42	16.70	-0.72	-7.54	0.00
Lag. Coups d'état	0.07	0.02	-0.05	-3.26	0.00
Lag. Armed conflict	0.03	0.007	-0.023	-2.59	0.01
Observations	271	1502			
	[1]	[2]	[3] = [2] - [1]	[4]	[5]
Panel B : After Weighting	Under US Sanctions	Without US Sanctions	Difference	t-Test	p-Value
Lag. GDP per Capita Growth	3.92	3.96	0.04	-0.16	0.87
Lag. Inflation	19.4	19.72	0.32	-0.06	0.95
Lag. Trade Openness	55.98	57.66	1.68	-1.33	0.18
Lag. Democracy	3.50	3.52	0.02	-0.28	0.78
Lag. Human Capital	2.16	2.16	0.00	-0.29	0.77
Lag. Population (Log)	17.42	17.37	-0.05	0.78	0.43
Lag. Coups d'état	0.07	0.07	-0.00	-0.20	0.84
Lag. Armed conflict	0.03	0.03	-0.023	0.22	0.82
Observations	271	1502			
Total of Weights	271	271			

5.2 Benchmark findings: treatment effects

This section presents the results of the impact of US economic sanctions on global value chains. Using the weights computed in Table 1, we estimate Eq.4 using Weighted Least Squares (WLS) in which the dependent variable is the GVCs' participation (measured as an index), and US economic sanctions is the treatment. Table 2 presents our baseline results. Column [1] presents the second step results of entropy balancing without country- and time-fixed effects. Columns [2–3] bring year and country fixed effects to the regressions, respectively, while column [4] jointly includes these two effects. Columns [5–8] repeat the exercise of columns [1–4] by gathering the matching covariates to the regression. Note that including matching covariates in the second step of the entropy balancing improves the matching quality (as in a randomized experiment), while controlling for country and year fixed effects removes all specific effects at country or year levels. Irrespective of the specification, the estimated effect of US sanctions on GVCs' participation is negative and statistically significant at the 1% threshold. This result ranges from 1.064 percentage points (column [8]) to 2.447 percentage points (column [1])—a robust result given the relative stability of the coefficients in the eight specifications of the table. Column [8] reports our benchmark results, with all covariates and time and country-fixed effects.

Econometric estimates suggest that US economic sanctions reduce GVC participation in sanctioned countries by an average of 1.06 percentage points (pp) compared to non-sanctioned countries. This result is economically significant, representing 10% of the standard deviation of GVCs participation. Furthermore, given that the average GVC value for non-sanctioned countries is 40.15 at the start and 46.06 at the end of the period studied, the average positive variation in GVC for these countries is 6 percentage points over 29 years (from 1990 to 2018). Thus, a reduction of 1.06 percentage points due to US sanctions implies that a sanctioned country loses, on average, almost 5 years of progress in global value chains. In other words, US sanctions lock targeted countries into international trade trajectories that considerably compromise their integration into the global economy if sanctions are

ever lifted. Consequently, our results support the notion that US economic sanctions result in lower GVCs’ participation in countries with sanctions compared to countries without sanctions, and the economic loss resulting from US economic sanctions is economically meaningful.

Table 2: US Sanctions and Global Values Chains.

GVCs’ participation	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
US sanctions	-2.447*** (0.703)	-1.464*** (0.464)	-2.389*** (0.658)	-1.147*** (0.276)	-1.969*** (0.609)	-1.087*** (0.307)	-1.917*** (0.589)	-1.064*** (0.276)
Country FE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Time FE	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Covariates	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

Notes : This Table presents the effects of US economic sanctions on Global Value Chains, estimated with the Weighted Least Squares (WLS). The baseline covariates include real GDP growth, inflation, trade openness-to-GDP, human capital index, population size, the degree of democracy, the number of coups d’état, and armed conflict—all lagged by one year to overcome reverse causality issues. All regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

6 Sensitivity checks

Our main empirical finding, shown in Table 2, supports the notion that US economic sanctions reduce GVCs’ participation in countries with sanctions compared to countries without sanctions. In this section, we run a range of economic and econometric tests to check the sensitivity of our results.

6.1 Alternative specifications

Our first robustness check re-estimates the benchmark model using alternative samples. Many countries experienced significant economic imbalances during the 2008–2009 global financial crisis (GFC) and other financial crises (including banking, currency, and debt crises), which may have adversely affected their participation in global value chains (GVCs).⁷ To avoid confounding effects, we exclude the GFC crisis and financial crises in columns [1] and [2] of Table A1, respectively. Another potential source of bias comes from episodes of hyperinflation, which could produce overlapping effects with US sanctions. To isolate the relationship between sanctions and GVC participation more accurately, we exclude cases where inflation rates exceeded 40%. Similarly, fragile states may introduce additional distortions. Countries classified by the IMF as having weak governance, limited administrative capacity, or chronic social and humanitarian crises may face significant obstacles to their GVCs’ participation. To account for these factors, we remove fragile states from our sample.⁸ The period of President Trump’s presidency also warrants consideration, given the sharp increase in US sanctions during his mandate. Between 2017 and 2018, US-issued sanctions rose from 30% to 40% of global sanctions (Kirikakha et al., 2021), which may distort our estimates. Moreover, this period witnessed a sharp increase in tariffs, whose effects may be confounded with those of sanctions. To mitigate this

⁷For instance, the GFC of 2007–2008 not only led to a slowdown in trade but also intensified the fragmentation of GVCs (Bellora and Fontagné, 2020; IMF, 2012).

⁸See IMF Policy Paper.

concern, we exclude these years from our analysis. Going further, countries that were sanctioned for more than half of the analysis period (over 15 years)⁹ or for the entire period¹⁰ could also disproportionately influence the results. These cases are excluded to avoid potential bias. To conclude, as sanctions near their end, their economic effects may weaken. Economic agents may anticipate the imminent lifting of sanctions and adjust their behavior accordingly, potentially reducing the impact on GVC participation. To address this, we conduct a final test excluding the last year of sanctions. The results, reported in columns [1]–[8] of Table A1, confirm that our benchmark findings remain robust across all these sample adjustments.

Our second robustness check involves considering additional covariates to deal with omitted variable bias. For this purpose, these additional covariates, drawn from the literature, are included progressively and separately by augmenting the benchmark model. The list of covariates includes fiscal balance, debt level (Debt-to-GDP ratio), foreign direct investment (FDI), natural resource rents, real exchange rate, economic globalization, government stability, law and order, quality of government, level of political terror, level of political violence, freedom of expression and civil liberties. All these covariates are lagged by one year to address the reverse causality issue. The results presented in columns [1]-[13] of Table A2 are closely similar to those of our benchmark model, reinforcing our findings: US sanctions lead to lower GVCs' participation in sanctioned countries compared to non-sanctioned countries. However, the gradual and separate inclusion of different controls only mitigates the omitted variable bias associated with each control included separately. Our results may still suffer from omitted variables linked to the set of additional covariates. To tackle this issue, we include all additional covariates simultaneously in column [14] of Table A2. Our conclusions remain qualitatively unchanged compared to the benchmark model in Table 2. Table A11 in the Appendix describes these variables and their data source.

6.2 Placebo Tests

Our results suggest that US economic sanctions reduce GVCs' participation. However, this estimated effect may be subject to some identification threats. Indeed, one might argue that the estimated effects could be attributable to confounding factors rather than the actual imposition of sanctions. Consequently, we perform some falsification tests to ensure that the effect we capture is genuinely due to US economic sanctions. First, we randomly assign treatment in the treated countries using placebo adoption dates. The intuition is that assigning random “placebo” adoption dates allows us to observe whether similar effects appear even when the treatment timing is false. If significant results emerge with false dates, it would suggest that the observed treatment effects might be due to underlying trends rather than the US sanctions themselves. The results of this are reported in Table A3, and show that random assignments to the treatment in our sample (column [1]) lead to no significant effect, suggesting that our findings are not a random event and are specific to US sanctions, thus reinforcing our conclusions.

⁹This allows us to exclude Cambodia, Ivory Coast, Fiji, India, Iran, Lebanon, Libya, Philippines, Syria, and Zimbabwe.

¹⁰Only two countries, Iran and Libya, were sanctioned throughout the whole period.

Second, US economic sanctions can significantly alter the economic environment of targeted countries. Consequently, one might argue that the effects we observe may not solely stem from the sanctions themselves but rather from the subsequent shifts in institutional, political, social, or economic conditions triggered by these sanctions. If this is the case, it would seriously threaten our identification. To address this concern, we adopt an approach similar to that of [Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2015](#); [Apeti and Edoh, 2023](#), constructing two new treatment variables that capture the effects of US sanctions within specified time windows: from one year before to one year after the sanctions and two years before to two years after. Therefore, we expect that the narrow time window defining our new US sanctions variable will yield a more robust estimate of its effect on GVCs' participation, as the (generally slow-changing) institutional, political, social, and economic environment is more likely to remain stable within these narrow time windows. Using entropy balancing, we test the robustness of our benchmark results with each of these variables as a treatment variable. The results are presented in Table [A3](#). Columns [2] to [3] report the results for one-year windows surrounding the US sanctions [1;1] and two-year windows [2;2]. The results from these different specifications, consistent with our benchmark findings, suggest that the effect of US sanctions is not driven by some potential changes in the political, economic, or institutional conditions following the imposition of US sanctions.

6.3 Beyond US sanctions

As mentioned earlier, our paper focuses on US sanctions. This choice relies on the existing literature, where the majority of papers focus on US sanctions (see, for example, [Amuzegar, 1997](#); [Torbat, 2005](#); [Biglaiser and Lektzian, 2011](#); [Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016](#); [Adam and Tsarsitalidou, 2019](#); [Kohl, 2021](#); [Gutmann et al., 2021, 2023](#); [Apeti and Edoh, 2024](#), among others). Despite these relevant reasons for focusing on US sanctions, we also test the sensitivity of our results by considering (i) sanctions from the most active senders, i.e., when the United States is joined by supranational organizations such as the United Nations (UN) or the European Union (EU),¹¹ and (ii) all sanctions, regardless of the sender. The results reported in columns [3] and [4] of Table [A5](#) show that our conclusions remain qualitatively unchanged. However, it is striking that when the analysis is expanded to include broader sanctioning actors—whether the most active senders or all sanctions regardless of the sanctioning country—the estimated coefficients (-0.76 and -0.75, respectively) are smaller in absolute value than in our baseline model. A possible explanation for this result is that broadening the measure of economic sanctions to include those imposed by the United Nations, the European Union or other sanctioning countries introduces significant heterogeneity in the treatment. Indeed, sanctions vary in severity, scope, and enforcement, with some being largely symbolic rather than economically restrictive. For instance, the imposition of sanctions by entities such as the European Union requires that everyone agrees on their legitimacy. That said, the effectiveness and the enforcement of its coercive measures, i.e., sanctions, diminish with the heterogeneity of the main member states with regard to their economic ties with the target countries ([Weber and Schneider, 2020](#); [Apeti and Edoh, 2024](#)). As a result, the broader measure of global sanctions (both active senders and all

¹¹See [Gutmann et al., 2023](#) for a similar approach.

sanctions) may capture cases where the impact on participation in GVCs is weaker or negligible, introducing noise into the estimation. This statistical noise attenuates the average estimated effect, leading to a lower bound coefficient (attenuation bias).

6.4 Alternative methods

On the econometric side, we perform additional sensitivity tests using alternative methods. Specifically, we re-estimate the benchmark model using instrumental variables and the selection on the observable method developed by [Oster \(2019\)](#).

IV Estimates. First, we rely on an IV (instrumental variables) approach to deal with the potential endogeneity of US sanctions. Indeed, our estimates may still suffer from reverse causality issues. For example, [Jing et al. \(2003\)](#) suggest that the imposition is endogenous to the political process and the specific outcomes the sender aims to achieve. In the context of sanctions, [Neuenkirch and Neumeier \(2015\)](#) also argue that sanctions may be imposed in response to environments perceived as unfavorable by the sanctioning state, meaning the negative effects associated with sanctions could reflect the direct impact of the target's own policies. In such cases, using instrumental variables is well-suited to address this issue, as instrumental variables allow controlling for potential endogeneity issues resulting from unobserved time-varying factors that may affect both the likelihood of being sanctioned and GVCs' participation. The challenge with this approach obviously consists of identifying the variables that affect the likelihood of being sanctioned but do not affect GVCs' participation other than through the effect of US sanctions. Consequently, our IV approach uses two instruments. First, we use an internal instrument, i.e., the lagged variable (by one year) of US sanctions. Indeed, US economic sanctions tend to be highly persistent; once a country is sanctioned, these measures are often extended or intensified over time. Consequently, past sanctions are frequently correlated with current sanctions. Second, we use an external instrument—the political proximity of the USA to the sanctioned countries. Political proximity to the United States could significantly influence the likelihood of a country being sanctioned.¹² Generally, countries that align closely with U.S. interests and values through shared policies, strategic alliances, or economic partnerships may be less likely to face sanctions, as these alignments often reflect mutual interests in stability, security, or trade. Conversely, countries that pursue policies contrary to US interests—such as aligning with rival powers, supporting US-designated terrorist organizations, or undermining democratic norms—are at greater risk of sanctions. However, as is well known, the validity of the exclusion restriction cannot be tested directly, but we can discuss potential violations of our identification assumptions. A violation of the exclusion restriction could arise if political proximity to the US directly affects the GVCs' participation, for example, through trade linkages. This is not a real issue, as our baseline controls include trade openness.

Before turning on the result of our variable of interest—US sanctions—we want to notice that the usual tests (see Table A4 in the Appendix) on the relevance and validity of the instruments confirm that these can plausibly be considered as good candidates. Second-stage estimates are reported in

¹²Political proximity to US represent the difference in UN votes with US

column [1], panel B of Table A4 and point to a significant and negative effect of US sanctions on GVCs' participation. More importantly, the new coefficient obtained from instrumental variables remains qualitatively close to that obtained from entropy.

The Oster (2019) method. Second, even if we try to address omitted variable bias by considering additional covariates, our estimates may still suffer from unobservable factors. Several methods have been recently developed to assess the sensitivity of results to omitted variable bias (Altonji et al., 2005; Oster, 2019). These methods estimate how much larger the selection on unobservables should be to change the research findings. Following Galletta and Giommoni (2022), Siu et al. (2023), and Sawadogo (2024), we implement the method of Oster (2019) in column [2], panel A of Table A4. The statistic δ indicates how much stronger the selection on unobservable variables would have to be compared to observable variables for the true ATT effect to be zero. For statistically significant variables, low δ values (i.e., δ between 0 and 1) signal a potential risk. In other words, higher δ values are associated with lower chances that omitted variable bias substantially affects our results. For the outcome variable, GVCs' participation, the value of δ 10.7 is greater than 1, which suggests that our findings are not affected by omitted variables.

7 Heterogeneity

Beyond the results suggested by the baseline model, it may be interesting to explore some heterogeneous effects related to the type of sanctions and some macroeconomic factors.

7.1 Do the type of sanctions matter?

As mentioned in subsection 4.2, the GSDB categorizes sanctions into various types, including trade and financial sanctions. As our core analysis includes both types of sanctions, this section aims to test whether the effect of US sanctions may differ depending on their type, i.e., trade or financial. In fact, Hufbauer et al. (2009) explain that different types of sanctions have different effects in several ways. They argue that trade sanctions may have a limited impact compared to financial sanctions since the disruption of financial flows may also disrupt international trade even without any explicit trade sanctions. To test this differential impact, we re-estimate our benchmark model (Eq.4), distinguishing between trade sanctions and financial sanctions. The results are reported in columns [1] - [2] of Table A5. Our findings reveal that, regardless of the type of sanctions imposed (trade or financial), the estimated effect is negative and statistically significant, with the coefficient for trade sanctions being slightly larger (-0.755 versus -0.698). This result is unsurprising as some researchers find that trade sanctions reduce trade flows (Felbermayr et al., 2020), a critical component of GVCs' participation (Beltramello et al., 2012).

7.2 Do macroeconomic factors matter?

Here, we examine other sources of heterogeneity, focusing on the degree of trade openness, the endowment of natural resources, and financial development. The degree of trade openness can amplify

the adverse effects of US economic sanctions on GVCs. Highly open economies are more reliant on international trade, which can make them particularly vulnerable to sanctions that restrict access to key markets or disrupt cross-border supply chains. While open economies may attempt to mitigate these effects by diversifying trade partners or rerouting supply chains, these adjustments are often costly and time-consuming, exposing them to immediate disruptions. As a result, we expect the effect of sanctions to be pronounced in countries with higher levels of trade openness.¹³ Next, we consider the heterogeneity of the effects of sanctions relative to the endowment of natural resources. Resource-endowed economies are naturally open to international trade, which makes them highly dependent on trade and financial flows to export their raw materials and products, which they rarely, if ever, process. Consequently, by disrupting access to key markets, sanctions hinder not only the export of these resources but also the import of technologies and expertise essential to their extraction and processing. These disruptions may spread throughout global value chains, as natural resources are often essential inputs for strategic sectors such as energy, manufacturing, and construction. As a result, sanctions could be expected to have an amplified effect in resource-rich countries. However, this effect could be mitigated, or even neutralized, by these countries' ability to circumvent sanctions. Indeed, resource-rich economies often adopt diversification strategies, notably by reorienting their trade towards other partners or exploring new markets.¹⁴ Finally, we consider financial development as a source of heterogeneity. A well-developed financial system can mitigate the adverse effects of sanctions on participation in GVCs by enhancing access to credit, diversifying financing sources, and sustaining productive investment. By providing local firms with alternative funding options, such as domestic credit or capital markets, a well-developed financial system can partially offset the decline in foreign direct investment (FDI) triggered by sanctions. This financial resilience may enable firms to maintain operations, invest in innovation, and upgrade their production processes—key elements for integration and competitiveness within GVCs. Moreover, as highlighted by [Okah Efogo \(2020\)](#), financial development has enhanced GVCs' participation in African countries, reinforcing the idea that a well-functioning financial system can act as a buffer against external shocks. By fostering firm efficiency, stimulating factor productivity, and facilitating technological advancements ([Midrigan and Xu, 2014](#); [Amador and Cabral, 2016](#); [Adalet McGowan et al., 2018](#)), well-functioning banks not only sustain economic activity but also help firms navigate restrictions, ensuring continued engagement in global production networks despite economic sanctions.

To investigate the heterogeneity in the effects of US sanctions across these factors, we adopt an interaction-based approach, interacting US sanctions with each heterogeneity factor. To ease the interpretation of our result, we plotted the marginal effect of US sanctions conditional to these factors in figure 4. The black line/slope represents the marginal effect of US sanctions, and the dotted lines indicate the 90% confidence interval for which the marginal effect is computed. A striking observation from the results is that the effect of sanctions on GVCs' participation amplifies with the openness of trade and the endowments of natural resources. However, the effects are less pronounced in coun-

¹³Furthermore, countries with a high level of trade openness are generally small, and may therefore be more vulnerable to US sanctions.

¹⁴For example, as we mentioned earlier, despite the sanctions imposed by the United States, a large proportion of Iran's oil is purchased by China.

tries with a high level of financial development.

8 Transmission channels

Our findings provide evidence that economic sanctions decrease GVCs' participation in sanctioned countries compared to non-sanctioned countries. What is still absent, however, is an assessment of the channels of influence through which economic sanctions decrease GVCs' participation. As a final step, this section empirically explores the relevance of the three¹⁵ identified channels discussed in section 2, i.e., the reduction of FDI entry, the decline in innovation capacity, and macroeconomic instability (through rising inflation and real effective exchange rate volatility). Following [Apeti, 2023](#); [Combes et al., 2024b](#); [Sawadogo, 2024](#); [Pafadnam, 2024](#) among others, our approach proceeds in two steps.

The first step of our approach tests the relationship between the potential channel mentioned above and GVCs' participation through univariate regressions estimated with the OLS estimator. This approach aims to see if the identified channels are correlated with the outcome variable, GVCs' participation, in our paper. The results reported in Panel A of Table [A6](#) show that FDI inflows and innovation are positively correlated with GVCs' participation, while inflation¹⁶ and real effective exchange rate volatility are negatively correlated with GVCs' participation. These findings suggest that the identified variables represent potentially some channels of influence channels through which economic sanction can shape GVCs' participation. However, it is important to note that the fact that channels correlate with GVCs' participation is a necessary but not sufficient condition for establishing the channels' validity. The sufficient condition would be to explore to what extent these potential channels are affected by the variable of interest, i.e., US sanctions. Consequently, the second step analyzes the effects of US sanctions on the identified channels by re-estimating Eq.4 using entropy balancing and replacing the outcome variable (GVCs' participation) with the channel. The results reported in Panel B of Table [A6](#) suggest that US sanctions reduce FDI inflows and innovation capacity while fueling inflation and exchange rate volatility. As a result, we can reasonably conclude that US sanctions decrease GVCs' participation by reducing FDI inflows and innovation, and driving inflation and exchange rate volatility.

9 Conclusion

In recent decades, the growing use of US sanctions has become a defining feature of global geopolitics, particularly in an era of heightened international rivalries and shifting power dynamics. Once seen as a tool of last resort, these sanctions, have increasingly shaped the landscape of modern trade,

¹⁵A fourth mechanism discussed in section 2—exclusion from international financial networks—has not been empirically tested. We cannot directly test this mechanism using the two-step approach, as it is inherently embedded in the imposition of sanctions, particularly financial sanctions. Consequently, the empirical evidence we provide on financial sanctions may be related to this mechanism.

¹⁶As we already control for the lagged inflation in the baseline covariates, we naturally exclude lagged inflation from the list of controls in column [3] (Panel B of Table [A6](#)), where the outcome variable is inflation rate.

with profound implications for global value chains (GVCs). Existing literature shows that participating in GVCs generally brings economic benefits in terms of higher competitiveness, accumulation of human capital and technological improvement in developing countries (see e.g. [Xing et al., 2023](#)). As geopolitical tensions escalate, the impact of these sanctions on international trade and global value chains in these countries is more relevant than ever.

In this study, we investigate the effect of US economic sanctions on the participation of target countries in GVCs, using a sample of 102 developing countries from 1990-2018. Our empirical analysis relies on entropy balancing to address self-selection associated with the imposition of sanctions and limit threats to identification. Estimates provide evidence that economic sanctions significantly decrease GVCs participation in target countries. These findings are economically relevant, as we find that US economic sanctions lead to a drop in participation in value chains in target countries by an average of 1.06 pp compared to non-target countries, which corresponds to 10% of the standard deviation of GVCs participation. These results remain robust across various robustness checks, including sample modifications, alternative specifications, placebo tests, and alternative methods. Moreover, our paper explores some heterogeneity tests related to the type of sanctions (e.g., trade vs financial), and key macroeconomic factors. More specifically, our findings reveal that (i) trade sanctions exert a slightly stronger effect than financial sanctions, and (ii) the effects of US sanctions are more pronounced in countries with high trade openness and abundant natural resources, whereas they are mitigated in countries with a well-developed financial system. Finally, we empirically show that the adverse effects of US sanctions on GVC participation are driven by reduced FDI inflows and innovation capacity, rising inflation, and exchange rate volatility.

Our paper extends the discussion on the use of alternatives to sanctions. Our findings show the harmful effects of sanctions on sanctioned economies through reduced participation in the GVC. More broadly, sanctions can lead to perverse effects, such as the rise of populism and authoritarian regimes, as seen in Cuba, North Korea, and Venezuela. So, in the first instance, dialogue and negotiation should be prioritized to avoid systematic recourse to sanctions. This diplomatic approach is particularly important for developing countries, where the economic and social costs of sanctions can be particularly damaging and where value chains help to create jobs and reduce poverty. Even if diplomacy fails to produce agreements between the parties involved, sanctions should be applied with caution and not as a means of expression in a way that is not warranted by their harmful effects. Likewise, one might wonder to what extent trade policy tools such as higher tariffs can serve as an alternative to full-scale trade embargoes, exerting economic pressure without completely severing trade ties. This opens a path for future research to compare the effects of trade tariffs and trade sanctions. Going further, our findings question the role of the World Trade Organization (WTO) in promoting open trade in the context of the growing use of sanctions, as they are an obstacle to free trade. The WTO must, therefore, actively address these tensions, working to balance trade liberalization with the need for policies that ensure cohesion and fairness in international relations.

The period of analysis for this article extends to 2018, the limit imposed by the availability of data on global value chains (GVCs). This limitation prevents the inclusion of more recent episodes of sanctions imposed towards the end of President Trump's term. The post-2018 period was also

characterized by Sino-American trade tensions, the imposition of new tariffs and disruptions related to the COVID-19 pandemic, which may have altered the structure and dynamics of GVCs. It would therefore be interesting for future works to take this limitation of our analysis into account.

References

- Adalet McGowan, M., Andrews, D., and Millot, V. (2018). The walking dead? zombie firms and productivity performance in oecd countries. *Economic Policy*, 33(96):685–736.
- Adam, A. and Tsarsitalidou, S. (2019). Do sanctions lead to a decline in civil liberties? *Public Choice*, 180(3):191–215.
- Adarov, A. and Stehrer, R. (2021). Implications of foreign direct investment, capital formation and its structure for global value chains. *The World Economy*, 44(11):3246–3299.
- Afesorgbor, S. K. (2019). The impact of economic sanctions on international trade: How do threatened sanctions compare with imposed sanctions? *European Journal of Political Economy*, 56:11–26.
- Afesorgbor, S. K. and Mahadevan, R. (2016). The impact of economic sanctions on income inequality of target states. *World Development*, 83:1–11.
- Ahn, D. P. and Ludema, R. D. (2020). The sword and the shield: The economics of targeted sanctions. *European Economic Review*, 130:103587.
- Altonji, J. G., Elder, T. E., and Taber, C. R. (2005). Selection on observed and unobserved variables: Assessing the effectiveness of catholic schools. *Journal of Political Economy*, 113(1):151–184.
- Amador, J. and Cabral, S. (2016). Global value chains: A survey of drivers and measures. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 30(2):278–301.
- Amuzegar, J. (1997). Iran's economy and the us sanctions. *The Middle East Journal*, pages 185–199.
- Antràs, P. (2020). Conceptual aspects of global value chains. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 34(3):551–574.
- Antràs, P. and Chor, D. (2022). Global value chains. *Handbook of international economics*, 5:297–376.
- Antràs, P. and De Gortari, A. (2020). On the geography of global value chains. *Econometrica*, 88(4):1553–1598.
- Apeti, A. E. (2023). Household welfare in the digital age: Assessing the effect of mobile money on household consumption volatility in developing countries. *World Development*, 161:106110.
- Apeti, A. E. and Edoh, E. D. (2023). Tax revenue and mobile money in developing countries. *Journal of Development Economics*, 161:103014.
- Apeti, A. E. and Edoh, E. D. (2024). Economic sanctions and sovereign debt default. *European Journal of Political Economy*, page 102571.
- Arslanalp, S., Eichengreen, B., and Simpson-Bell, C. (2023). Gold as international reserves: A barbarous relic no more? *Journal of International Economics*, 145:103822.

- Balima, H. and Sy, A. (2021). Imf-supported programs and sovereign debt crises. *IMF Economic Review*, 69(2):427.
- Balima, H. W. (2020). Coups d'état and the cost of debt. *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 48(3):509–528.
- Barry, C. M. and Kleinberg, K. B. (2015). Profiting from sanctions: Economic coercion and us foreign direct investment in third-party states. *International Organization*, 69(4):881–912.
- Bellora, C. and Fontagné, L. G. (2020). Shooting oneself in the foot? trade war and global value chains.
- Beltramello, A., De Backer, K., and Moussiég, L. (2012). The export performance of countries within global value chains (gvcs).
- Biglaiser, G. and Lektzian, D. (2011). The effect of sanctions on us foreign direct investment. *International Organization*, 65(3):531–551.
- Bjørnskov, C. and Rode, M. (2020). Regime types and regime change: A new dataset on democracy, coups, and political institutions. *The Review of International Organizations*, 15(2):531–551.
- Bruno, R. L., Cipollina, M., and Dal Bianco, S. (2024). Trade sanctions and global value chains: A china-south africa perspective in the age of sanctions. *China Economic Review*, page 102300.
- Casella, B., Bolwijn, R., Moran, D., and Kanemoto, K. (2019). Improving the analysis of global value chains: the unctad-eora database. *Transnational Corporations*, 26(3):115–142.
- Caselli, F. and Wingender, P. (2021). Heterogeneous effects of fiscal rules: The maastricht fiscal criterion and the counterfactual distribution of government deficits. *European Economic Review*, 136:103748.
- Chen, G., Geiger, M., and Fu, M. (2015). Manufacturing fdi in Sub-Saharan Africa: trends, determinants, and impacts.
- Combes, J.-L., Debrun, X., Minea, A., Sawadogo, P. N., and Vinturis, C. (2024a). On the side effects of fiscal policy: Fiscal rules and income inequality. *European Journal of Political Economy*, page 102534.
- Combes, J.-L., Kaba, K., Minea, A., et al. (2024b). Inflation targeting and firm performance in developing countries. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 163:104854.
- Coppedge, M., Gerring, J., Knutsen, C. H., Lindberg, S. I., Teorell, J., Altman, D., Angiolillo, F., Bernhard, M., Borella, C., Cornell, A., et al. (2024). V-dem codebook v14.
- Cortright, D. and Lopez, G. A. (2000). *The sanctions decade: Assessing UN strategies in the 1990s*. Lynne Rienner Publishers.
- Crozet, M., Hinz, J., Stammann, A., and Wanner, J. (2021). Worth the pain? firms' exporting behaviour to countries under sanctions. *European Economic Review*, 134:103683.

- Damijan, J. P. and Kostevc, Č. (2015). Learning from trade through innovation. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 77(3):408–436.
- Demir, F. (2013). Growth under exchange rate volatility: Does access to foreign or domestic equity markets matter? *Journal of Development Economics*, 100(1):74–88.
- Doamba, M. U. (2025). Mining and structural change: How does mining affect participation in the global value chain? *Economics of Transition and Institutional Change*.
- Eaton, J. and Engers, M. (1999). Sanctions: Some simple analytics. *American Economic Review*, 89(2):409–414.
- Fadaee, M. and Derakhshan, M. (2015). Analysis of short run and long run effects of economic sanctions on economic growth in iran. *Quarterly Journal of Economic Growth and Development Research*, 5(18):132–113.
- Feenstra, R. C., Inklaar, R., and Timmer, M. P. (2015). The next generation of the penn world table. *American Economic Review*, 105(10):3150–3182.
- Felbermayr, G., Kirilakha, A., Syropoulos, C., Yalcin, E., and Yotov, Y. (2022). The ‘global sanctions data base’: Mapping international sanction policies from 1950-2019. *Global Economic Consequences of the War in Ukraine Sanctions, Supply Chains and Sustainability*.
- Felbermayr, G., Kirilakha, A., Syropoulos, C., Yalcin, E., and Yotov, Y. V. (2020). The global sanctions data base. *European Economic Review*, 129:103561.
- Fernandes, A. M., Kee, H. L., and Winkler, D. (2022). Determinants of global value chain participation: Cross-country evidence. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 36(2):329–360.
- Galletta, S. and Giommoni, T. (2022). The effect of the 1918 influenza pandemic on income inequality: Evidence from Italy. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 104(1):187–203.
- Ghorbani Dastgerdi, H., Yusof, Z. B., and Shahbaz, M. (2018). Nexus between economic sanctions and inflation: a case study in Iran. *Applied Economics*, 50(49):5316–5334.
- Golikova, V. and Kuznetsov, B. (2017). Perception of risks associated with economic sanctions: The case of russian manufacturing. *Post-Soviet Affairs*, 33(1):49–62.
- Gutmann, J., Neuenkirch, M., and Neumeier, F. (2021). Sanctioned to death? the impact of economic sanctions on life expectancy and its gender gap. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 57(1):139–162.
- Gutmann, J., Neuenkirch, M., and Neumeier, F. (2023). The economic effects of international sanctions: An event study. *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 51(4):1214–1231.
- Gygli, S., Haelg, F., Potrafke, N., and Sturm, J.-E. (2019). The KOF Globalisation Index–Revisited. *The Review of International Organizations*, 14:543–574.

- Haidar, J. I. (2017). Sanctions and export deflection: evidence from Iran. *Economic Policy*, 32(90):319–355.
- Hainmueller, J. (2012). Entropy balancing for causal effects: A multivariate reweighting method to produce balanced samples in observational studies. *Political Analysis*, 20(1):25–46.
- Hatipoglu, E., Soytas, M. A., and Belaïd, F. (2023). Environmental consequences of geopolitical crises: the case of economic sanctions and emissions. *Resources Policy*, 85:104011.
- Heckman, J. J., Ichimura, H., Smith, J. A., and Todd, P. (1998). Characterizing selection bias using experimental data. *NBER Working Paper*, (w6699).
- Heine-Ellison, S. (2001). The impact and effectiveness of multilateral economic sanctions: A comparative study. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 5(1):81–112.
- Huang, H.-C. and Yeh, C.-C. (2014). Inflation targeting on unemployment rates: A quantile treatment effect approach. *Applied Economics Letters*, 21(7):453–458.
- Hufbauer, G. C., Schott, J. J., and Elliott, K. A. (2009). Economic sanctions reconsidered. *Peterson Institute Press: All Books*.
- IMF (2012). *Regional Economic Outlook, April 2012, Western Hemisphere*. International Monetary Fund.
- Itskhoki, O. and Mukhin, D. (2022). Sanctions and the exchange rate. Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Janeba, E. (2024). Extraterritorial trade sanctions: Theory and application to the US–Iran–EU conflict. *Review of International Economics*, 32(1):49–71.
- Jing, C., Kaempfer, W. H., and Lowenberg, A. D. (2003). Instrument choice and the effectiveness of international sanctions: A simultaneous equations approach. *Journal of Peace Research*, 40(5):519–535.
- Joshi, S., Mahmud, A. S., Nandy, A., and Sarangi, S. (2024). Sanctions in directed trade networks. *Review of International Economics*, 32(1):72–108.
- Kaempfer, W. H. and Lowenberg, A. D. (1988). The theory of international economic sanctions: A public choice approach. *The American Economic Review*, 78(4):786–793.
- Kandilov, I. T. and Leblebicioğlu, A. (2011). The impact of exchange rate volatility on plant-level investment: Evidence from Colombia. *Journal of Development Economics*, 94(2):220–230.
- Kee, H. L. (2015). Local intermediate inputs and the shared supplier spillovers of foreign direct investment. *Journal of Development Economics*, 112:56–71.
- Kee, H. L. and Tang, H. (2016). Domestic value added in exports: Theory and firm evidence from china. *American Economic Review*, 106(6):1402–1436.

- Khachoo, Q. and Sharma, R. (2016). Fdi and innovation: An investigation into intra-and inter-industry effects. *Global Economic Review*, 45(4):311–330.
- Kinda, H. and Mien, E. (2024). Does transparency pay? natural resources, financial development and the extractive industries transparency initiative (eiti). *World Development*, 179:106603.
- Kirikakha, A., Felbermayr, G. J., Syropoulos, C., Yalcin, E., and Yotov, Y. V. (2021). The global sanctions data base (gsdb): an update that includes the years of the trump presidency. In *Research handbook on economic sanctions*, pages 62–106. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Kohl, T. (2021). In and out of the penalty box: Us sanctions and their effects on international trade. In *Research Handbook on Economic Sanctions*, pages 388–410. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Korhonen, I. (2019). Sanctions and counter-sanctions: What are their economic effects in russia and elsewhere? Technical report, BOFIT Policy Brief.
- Kose, M. A., Kurlat, S., Ohnsorge, F., and Sugawara, N. (2022). A cross-country database of fiscal space. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 128:102682.
- Kowalski, P. (2015). Participation of developing countries in global value chains: Implications for trade and trade-related policies.
- Lacy, D. and Niou, E. M. (2004). A theory of economic sanctions and issue linkage: The roles of preferences, information, and threats. *The Journal of Politics*, 66(1):25–42.
- Laudati, D. and Pesaran, M. H. (2023). Identifying the effects of sanctions on the iranian economy using newspaper coverage. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 38(3):271–294.
- Le, H. T., Hoang, D. P., Doan, T. N., Pham, C. H., and To, T. T. (2022). Global economic sanctions, global value chains and institutional quality: Empirical evidence from cross-country data. *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 31(3):427–449.
- Lektzian, D. and Biglaiser, G. (2013). Investment, opportunity, and risk: Do us sanctions deter or encourage global investment? *International Studies Quarterly*, 57(1):65–78.
- Mamonov, M. and Pestova, A. (2022). The price of war: Macroeconomic and cross-sectional effects of sanctions on Russia. *Available at SSRN 4190655*.
- Mancini, M., Montalbano, P., Nenci, S., and Vurchio, D. (2024). Positioning in global value chains: World map and indicators, a new dataset available for gvc analyses. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 38(4):669–690.
- Martínez-Galán, E. and Fontoura, M. P. (2019). Global value chains and inward foreign direct investment in the 2000s. *The World Economy*, 42(1):175–196.
- Mayer, T., Santoni, G., and Vicard, V. (2023). *The CEPII trade and production database*. CEPII.

- McLean, E. V. and Whang, T. (2010). Friends or foes? major trading partners and the success of economic sanctions. *International Studies Quarterly*, 54(2):427–447.
- Midrigan, V. and Xu, D. Y. (2014). Finance and misallocation: Evidence from plant-level data. *American Economic Review*, 104(2):422–458.
- Mirkina, I. (2018). Fdi and sanctions: An empirical analysis of short-and long-run effects. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 54:198–225.
- Mityakov, S., Tang, H., and Tsui, K. K. (2013). International politics and import diversification. *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 56(4):1091–1121.
- Montalbano, P., Nenci, S., and Pietrobelli, C. (2018). Opening and linking up: firms, gvcs, and productivity in Latin America. *Small Business Economics*, 50(4):917–935.
- Morgan, T. C., Syropoulos, C., and Yotov, Y. V. (2023). Economic sanctions: Evolution, consequences, and challenges. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 37(1):3–29.
- Morrison, A., Pietrobelli, C., and Rabelotti, R. (2008). Global value chains and technological capabilities: a framework to study learning and innovation in developing countries. *Oxford Development Studies*, 36(1):39–58.
- Moteng, G., Raghutla, C., Njangang, H., and Nembot, L. N. (2023). International sanctions and energy poverty in target developing countries. *Energy Policy*, 179:113629.
- Neuenkirch, M. and Neumeier, F. (2015). The impact of un and us economic sanctions on gdp growth. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 40:110–125.
- Neuenkirch, M. and Neumeier, F. (2016). The impact of us sanctions on poverty. *Journal of Development Economics*, 121:110–119.
- Nguyen, T. C., Castro, V., and Wood, J. (2022). A new comprehensive database of financial crises: Identification, frequency, and duration. *Economic Modelling*, 108:105770.
- Nguyen, T. T. and Do, M. H. (2021). Impact of economic sanctions and counter-sanctions on the russian federation's trade. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 71:267–278.
- Nosratabadi, J. (2023). The impact of trade sanctions on the relative demand for skilled labor and wages: Evidence from Iran. *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 32(2):219–239.
- Oechslin, M. (2014). Targeting autocrats: Economic sanctions and regime change. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 36:24–40.
- Ogrokhina, O. and Rodriguez, C. M. (2019). The effect of inflation targeting and financial openness on currency composition of sovereign international debt. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 97:1–18.

- Ogrokhina, O. and Rodriguez, C. M. (2024). Inflation targeting and capital flows: A tale of two cycles in developing countries. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, page 103121.
- Okah Efogo, F. (2020). Financial development and african participation in global value chains. *Financing Africa's Development: Paths to Sustainable Economic Growth*, pages 33–52.
- Oster, E. (2019). Unobservable selection and coefficient stability: Theory and evidence. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 37(2):187–204.
- Pafadnam, N. A. R. (2024). How does implementing the extractive industries transparency initiative (eiti) affect economic growth? evidence from developing countries. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 85:102584.
- Peksen, D. (2009). Better or worse? the effect of economic sanctions on human rights. *Journal of Peace Research*, 46(1):59–77.
- Peksen, D. and Drury, A. C. (2010). Coercive or corrosive: The negative impact of economic sanctions on democracy. *International Interactions*, 36(3):240–264.
- Rashid, A. and Waqar, S. M. (2017). Exchange rate fluctuations, firm size, and export behavior: An empirical investigation. *Small Business Economics*, 49:609–625.
- Raymond, E., April, K., Sergey, M., and Margarita, P. (2022). Political beta. *Review of Finance*, 26(5):1179–1215.
- Sawadogo, R. F. (2024). Do fiscal rules shape private-sector investment decisions? *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 81:103617.
- Shin, G., Choi, S.-W., and Luo, S. (2016). Do economic sanctions impair target economies? *International Political Science Review*, 37(4):485–499.
- Shingal, A. (2024). Economic sanctions and domestic diversion. *Economics Letters*, page 111999.
- Siu, J., Sterck, O., and Rodgers, C. (2023). The freedom to choose: Theory and quasi-experimental evidence on cash transfer restrictions. *Journal of Development Economics*, 161:103027.
- Smith, J. A. and Todd, P. E. (2005). Does matching overcome lalonde's critique of nonexperimental estimators? *Journal of Econometrics*, 125(1-2):305–353.
- Syropoulos, C., Felbermayr, G., Kirilakha, A., Yalcin, E., and Yotov, Y. V. (2024). The global sanctions data base–release 3: Covid-19, Russia, and multilateral sanctions. *Review of International Economics*, 32(1):12–48.
- Tajoli, L. and Felice, G. (2018). Global value chains participation and knowledge spillovers in developed and developing countries: An empirical investigation. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 30:505–532.

- Teorell, J., Dahlberg, S., Holmberg, S., Rothstein, B., Khomenko, A., and Svensson, R. (2016). The quality of government standard dataset, version jan16. *University of Gothenburg: The Quality of Government Institute*, <http://www.qog.pol.gu.se/doi>, 10.
- Tian, K., Dietzenbacher, E., and Jong-A-Pin, R. (2022). Global value chain participation and its impact on industrial upgrading. *The World Economy*, 45(5):1362–1385.
- Torbat, A. E. (2005). Impacts of the US trade and financial sanctions on Iran. *World Economy*, 28(3):407–434.
- Tsebelis, G. (1990). Are sanctions effective? a game-theoretic analysis. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 34(1):3–28.
- Wang, Y., Wang, K., and Chang, C.-P. (2019). The impacts of economic sanctions on exchange rate volatility. *Economic Modelling*, 82:58–65.
- Weber, P. M. and Schneider, G. (2020). How many hands to make sanctions work? comparing eu and us sanctioning efforts. *European Economic Review*, 130:103595.
- Wen, J., Zhao, X., and Chang, C.-P. (2024). The impact of international sanctions on innovation of target countries. *Economics & Politics*, 36(1):39–79.
- Xing, Y., Wang, R., and Dollar, D. (2023). Global value chain development report 2023: Resilient and sustainable gvcs in turbulent times.
- Yang, Z. (2023). The US-China trade war and global value chains.
- Ye, Y. and Zhang, Q. (2024). The futility of economic sanctions in a globalized and interdependent world: a data-driven game theoretical study. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1):1–10.

Appendix

Table A1: Robustness check: Alternative samples.

	GFC (2008-2009)	Financial Crises	Hyperinflation ep.	Fragile States
GVCs' participation	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
US sanctions	-1.096*** (0.287)	-0.562* (0.303)	-1.093*** (0.284)	-1.092*** (0.313)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1565	1619	1035	1506

	Trump Presidency	Half-Time Sanctionned	Always Sanctionned	Last year of sanctions
GVCs' participation	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
US sanctions	-0.924*** (0.278)	-0.938*** (0.294)	-1.081*** (0.276)	-1.372*** (0.256)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1567	1588	1667	1649

Notes: This table displays the sensitivity checks of Eq. 4 using alternative samples. Columns [1]–[3] exclude periods associated with the Global Financial Crisis (2008–2009), other financial crises (including banking, currency, and debt crises), and episodes of hyperinflation, respectively. Columns [4]–[5] exclude fragile states, the Trump presidency, respectively. Columns [6]–[7] exclude countries subjected to sanctions for more than half or the entirety of the analysis period. Column [8] excludes the last year of sanctions. The baseline covariates include real GDP growth, inflation, trade openness-to-GDP, human capital index, population size, the degree of democracy, the number of coups d'état, and armed conflict—all lagged by one year to overcome reverse causality issues. All regressions include weights, and the constant is not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Table A2: Robustness check: Adding Controls.

	Fiscal Balance	Debt-to GDP ratio	FDI	Natural Resource Rents	Exchange rate
GVCs' participation	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
US sanctions	-1.147*** (0.278)	-0.760** (0.310)	-1.051*** (0.277)	-1.052*** (0.273)	-1.057*** (0.277)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1551	1324	1690	1690	1695
	Economic Glo.	Political Stab.	Law and Order	Quality of Gov.	Political Terror
GVCs' participation	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]
US sanctions	-1.103*** (0.289)	-1.054*** (0.275)	-1.083*** (0.274)	-0.947*** (0.262)	-1.116*** (0.303)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1668	1695	1695	1693	1484
	Political Violence	Freedom of Expression	Civil Liberties	All Additional Controls	
GVCs' participation	[11]	[12]	[13]	[14]	
US sanctions	-1.179*** (0.276)	-1.023*** (0.272)	-0.984*** (0.274)	-0.909*** (0.313)	
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Observations	1695	1695	1695	1130	

Notes: This table displays the sensitivity checks of Eq.4 using alternative specifications. For this purpose, Columns [1] – [13] check the baseline sensitivity by considering additional controls—drawn from the literature—that are separately and progressively added in the baseline model (Eq.4). The list of additional covariates includes fiscal balance, debt level (Debt-to-GDP ratio), foreign direct investment (FDI), natural resource rents, real exchange rate, economic globalization, government stability, law and order, quality of government, level of political terror, level of political violence, freedom of expression and civil liberties. Column [14] includes all additional controls at once. The baseline covariates include real GDP growth, inflation, trade openness-to-GDP, human capital index, population size, the degree of democracy, the number of coups d'état, and armed conflict—all lagged by one year to overcome reverse causality issues. All regressions include weights, and the constant is not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Table A3: Robustness check: Falsification Tests.

GVCs' participation	[1]	[2]	[3]
Placebo US	-0.002 (0.220)		
[-1;1]		-0.961*** (0.359)	
[-2;2]			-0.723** (0.333)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1037	1480	1514

Notes: This table displays the sensitivity checks of Eq.4 related to falsification tests. Column [1] presents the results of the placebo test related to treatment random assignment in our sample. Columns [2] - [3] constrain the treatment period, considering a window of one and two years, respectively. The baseline covariates include real GDP growth, inflation, trade openness-to-GDP, human capital index, population size, the degree of democracy, the number of coups d'état, and armed conflict—all lagged by one year to overcome reverse causality issues. All regressions include weights, and the constant is not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 .

Table A4: Robustness check: Alternative Methods.

	IV	Oster (2019)
GVCs' participation	[1]	[2]
Panel A: Alternative Methods		
US sanctions	-0.723** (0.339)	-1.064*** (0.290)
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat.	324.68	
Kleibergen-Paap LM-stat. p-val.	0.00	
Sargan-Hansen	0.56	
Delta		10.70
Country FE	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes
Covariates	Yes	Yes
Observations	1631	1695
Panel B: First Stage Equation		
Political Proximity	0.773*** (0.031)	
Lag. US Sanctions	0.042* (0.023)	

Notes: This table displays the sensitivity checks of Eq.4 using alternative methods (panel A). In column [1], we instrument the US sanctions with the political proximity of the USA and the lag (by one year) of US sanctions. Column [2] performs the Oster (2019) test on the selection of observables. Finally, panel B presents the results of the first stage equation. The baseline covariates include real GDP growth, inflation, trade openness-to-GDP, human capital index, population size, the degree of democracy, the number of coups d'état, and armed conflict—all lagged by one year to overcome reverse causality issues. All regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table A5: Heterogeneity (2/3) : Type of Sanctions

GVCs' participation	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
US Trade sanctions	-0.755*** (0.267)			
US Financial sanctions		-0.698** (0.287)		
Active senders			-0.757** (0.307)	
All sanctions				-0.753*** (0.268)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1695	1695	1695	1695

Notes: This table displays the heterogeneity results considering the type of US sanctions. Columns [1] - [2] report the results for US trade and financial sanctions, respectively. Columns [3] - [4] report the results of our sensitivity check on alternative definitions of sanctions. Active senders in Column [3] refer to sanctions when the United States is joined by the United Nations (UN) or the European Union (EU). All sanctions in column [4] refer to sanctions, regardless of the sender. All regressions include the constant not reported in the table. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1 .

Table A6: Channels of Influence

GVCs participation	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
Panel A: Correlation between Potential Channels and GVCs participation				
FDI Inflows	0.204*** (0.042)			
Innovation		1.612*** (0.117)		
Inflation			-1.099*** (0.159)	
Exchange Rate Volatility				-0.230*** (0.067)
Observations	2631	1528	2522	2609
Panel B: Regression of the Potential Channel on the Treatment Variable				
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
	FDI Inflows	Innovation	Inflation	Exchange Rate Volatility
US sanctions	-0.176** (0.082)	-0.181** (0.087)	0.185*** (0.057)	0.224** (0.090)
Observations	1655	1224	1718	1771

Notes: This table displays the results for the channels of influence. Panel A reports the results of univariate regression estimates of FDI inflows, innovation, inflation and exchange rate volatility, and interest rate volatility on GVCs participation using the OLS estimator. In Panel B, we re-estimate our baseline model using entropy balancing and replacing our outcome variable with the potential channel. Robust standard errors are in brackets. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1

Figure 4: Heterogeneity: Exploring conditional effects related to macroeconomic and institutional factors.

Table A7: List of Countries

Afghanistan ^a	Guinea ^a	Nigeria ^a
Albania	Guinea-Bissau ^a	Oman
Algeria	Guyana	Pakistan ^a
Angola ^a	Haiti ^a	Panama ^a
Argentina	Honduras ^a	Papua New Guinea
Armenia	Hungary	Paraguay
Azerbaijan ^a	India ^a	Peru ^a
Bangladesh	Indonesia ^a	Philippines ^a
Benin	Iran, Islamic Rep. ^a	Poland
Bolivia ^a	Iraq ^a	Romania ^a
Botswana	Jamaica ^a	Russian Federation ^a
Brazil	Jordan	Rwanda
Bulgaria	Kazakhstan	Saudi Arabia ^a
Burkina Faso ^a	Kenya ^a	Senegal
Burundi ^a	Kyrgyz Republic	Sierra Leone ^a
Cambodia ^a	Lao PDR ^a	Somalia ^a
Cameroon ^a	Lebanon ^a	South Africa ^a
Central African Republic ^a	Lesotho	Sri Lanka
Chad	Liberia ^a	Syrian Arab Republic ^a
Chile ^a	Libya ^a	Tajikistan
China ^a	Madagascar ^a	Tanzania ^a
Colombia ^a	Malawi ^a	Thailand ^a
Costa Rica ^a	Malaysia	Togo
Cote d'Ivoire ^a	Mali ^a	Tunisia
Djibouti	Mauritania ^a	Turkey ^a
Dominican Republic ^a	Mauritius	Uganda
Ecuador ^a	Mexico	Ukraine ^a
Egypt, Arab Rep. ^a	Mongolia	Uruguay
Ethiopia ^a	Morocco	Uzbekistan
Fiji ^a	Mozambique	Venezuela, RB ^a
Gabon	Namibia	Vietnam
Georgia	Nepal	Yemen, Rep.
Ghana ^a	Nicaragua ^a	Zambia ^a
Guatemala ^a	Niger ^a	Zimbabwe ^a

Note: ^a refers to countries under US sanctions.

Table A8: List of Countries by Type of US sanctions (trade or financial)

Afghanistan ^b	Guinea ^f	Nigeria ^b
Albania	Guinea-Bissau ^f	Oman
Algeria	Guyana	Pakistan ^b
Angola ^b	Haiti ^b	Panama ^b
Argentina	Honduras ^f	Papua New Guinea
Armenia	Hungary	Paraguay
Azerbaijan ^f	India ^b	Peru ^f
Bangladesh	Indonesia ^b	Philippines ^f
Benin	Iran, Islamic Rep. ^b	Poland
Bolivia ^b	Iraq ^b	Romania ^b
Botswana	Jamaica ^b	Russian Federation ^b
Brazil	Jordan	Rwanda
Bulgaria	Kazakhstan	Saudi Arabia ^b
Burkina Faso ^f	Kenya ^f	Senegal
Burundi ^f	Kyrgyz Republic	Sierra Leone ^b
Cambodia ^b	Lao PDR ^f	Somalia ^b
Cameroon ^b	Lebanon ^b	South Africa ^t
Central African Republic ^f	Lesotho	Sri Lanka
Chad	Liberia ^b	Syrian Arab Republic ^b
Chile ^f	Libya ^b	Tajikistan
China ^b	Madagascar ^f	Tanzania ^f
Colombia ^b	Malawi ^f	Thailand ^f
Costa Rica ^b	Malaysia	Togo
Cote d'Ivoire ^f	Mali ^b	Tunisia
Djibouti	Mauritania ^f	Turkey ^b
Dominican Republic ^b	Mauritius	Uganda
Ecuador ^f	Mexico	Ukraine ^b
Egypt, Arab Rep. ^f	Mongolia	Uruguay
Ethiopia ^f	Morocco	Uzbekistan
Fiji ^f	Mozambique	Venezuela, RB ^b
Gabon	Namibia	Vietnam
Georgia	Nepal	Yemen, Rep.
Ghana ^b	Nicaragua ^b	Zambia ^f
Guatemala ^f	Niger ^b	Zimbabwe ^f

Note: ^t refers to countries under US trade sanctions, ^f refers to countries under US financial sanctions, ^b refers to countries under both US sanctions (trade and financial).

Table A9: Descriptive Statistics of the Main Variables

	Obs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
US sanctions	2958	0.1677	0.3736	0	1
GVCs' participation	2697	45.0620	10.6943	22.7553	82.6092
Real GDP growth	2913	3.8764	6.7691	-64.0471	106.2798
Inflation	2613	27.9282	236.3820	-16.8597	7481.664
Trade Openness	2683	70.6776	35.5682	0.0210	347.9965
Human Capital Index	2581	2.1236	0.5896	1.0296	3.5009
Population (Log)	2958	16.4357	1.4294	13.2659	21.0617
Democracy	2373	3.5044	1.4350	0.0000	6.0000
Coups d'état	2958	0.0416	0.2128	0	2
Armed Conflict	2958	0.0139	0.1169	0	1

Table A10: Summary of data sources and variable definitions (1/2)

Variable	Definition	Source
GVCs participation		
GVCs participation	Index ranging from 0 to 100.	Authors' calculations.
Backward participation	Index ranging from 0 to 100.	Authors' calculations.
Forward participation	Index ranging from 0 to 100.	Authors' calculations.
Sanctions		
US economic sanctions	Dummy equal to one if a country is under US trade or financial sanctions in year t and zero otherwise.	Kirikakha et al. (2021) .
US trade sanctions	Dummy equal to one if a country is under US trade sanctions in year t and zero otherwise.	Kirikakha et al. (2021) .
US financial sanctions	Dummy equal to one if a country is under US financial sanctions in year t and zero otherwise.	Kirikakha et al. (2021) .
UN sanctions	Dummy variable taking one if a country is subject to UN economic sanctions in year t and zero otherwise.	Kirikakha et al. (2021) .
EU sanctions	Dummy variable taking one if a country is subject to EU economic sanctions in year t and zero otherwise.	Kirikakha et al. (2021) .
Other sanctions	Dummy variable taking one if a country is subject to economic sanctions, regardless of the sender in year t and zero otherwise.	Kirikakha et al. (2021) .
Covariates		
Real GDP growth	Annual percentage growth rate of real GDP.	WDI , World Bank.
Inflation	Inflation, average consumer prices (% change).	WDI , World Bank.
Trade openness	Sum of exports and imports of goods and services as a % of GDP.	WDI , World Bank.
Democracy	Index ranging from 0 to 6.	ICRG .
Human capital	Human capital index based on years of schooling and returns to education.	PWT , Feenstra et al. (2015) .
Population (Log)	Total population.	WDI , World Bank.
Coups d'État	Number of coups d'état in a country.	Bjørnskov and Rode (2020) .
Conflict	International armed conflict indicator.	Coppedge et al. (2024) .

Table A11: Summary of data sources and variable definitions (2/2)

Variable	Definition	Source
Other Variables		
Fiscal balance	Fiscal balance as a percentage of GDP.	Kose et al. (2022)
Public debt	Government total public debt as a percentage of GDP.	PFMHD , International Monetary Fund.
FDI (log)	Foreign direct investment, net inflows (current US\$).	WDI , World Bank.
Natural resources endowments	Total natural resources rents as a percentage of GDP.	WDI , World Bank.
Real exchange rate	Real effective exchange rate.	PWT , Feenstra et al. (2015) .
KOF Economic Globalization index (overall)	Index ranging from 1 to 100.	Gygli et al. (2019) .
Government stability	Index ranging from 0 to 12.	ICRG .
Law and order	Index ranging from 0 to 6.	ICRG .
Quality of government	Indicator of quality of governance ranging from 0 to 1.	ICRG .
Political terror scale	Scale measuring physical integrity rights violations (1-5).	Political Terror Scale.
Political violence	The use of physical force to achieve political objectives by non-state actors (ranging from -3.5 to 4.2).	Coppedge et al. (2024) .
Civil liberties	Civil liberties index (higher value = fewer civil liberties).	Teorell et al. (2016) .
Freedom of expression	Freedom of expression index ranging from 0 to 1.	Coppedge et al. (2024) .
Financial Crises	Dummy equal to one if financial crises (banking currency or debt) at year t in a given country and zero otherwise.	SBCD , Nguyen et al. (2022) .
Innovation	Number of patents applications held by residents and nonresidents.	WDI , World Bank.
Real effective exchange rate volatility	The standard deviation of a three-year moving average of real effective exchange rate.	Authors' calculations from Feenstra et al. (2015) .
Political Proximity	Difference in UN voting disagreement score with USA	CEPII Database , Mayer et al. (2023)